

ART FRONTIER

An International Art Journal /Vol.2, No.1 Jan.-Mar, 2024

A Study of the Characteristics and Aesthetic Orientation of He Shaoji's Brushwork

Hao Chunyan

To cite this article: Hao Chunyan, "A Study of the Characteristics and Aesthetic Orientation of He Shaoji's Brushwork," *Art Frontier* 2, no.1 (March 2024): 98-106, <https://doi.org/10.64212/LVAS5686>.

DOI: 10.64212/LVAS5686

ISSN: 2835-5490

EISSN: 2836-841X

© 2024 Frontier Press.

This article is published under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). For full license details, please visit: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

This article has undergone double-blind peer review.

Website: www.artfrontier.org

Email: artfrontier2023@outlook.com

Publishing Frequency: Quarterly (March, June, September, December)

A Study of the Characteristics and Aesthetic Orientation of He Shaoji's Brushwork

Hao Chunyan

Abstract

He Shaoji is one of the representative artists of Chinese calligraphy art from the Qing Dynasty. Amidst the prevailing trend of “depreciating the Tang style” in epigraphy, he keenly recognized the important value of the complementary relationship between rubbing study and stele study, formed the brushwork view of horizontal and vertical strokes, and studied the impact of seal script and official script (精古篆分) on the innovation of integrating dialogue. Thus, these formed the aesthetic characteristics of his calligraphy: simple but rounded strokes with internal strength and natural variations. The brushwork technique is crucial in He Shaoji's calligraphic art, indicating his theoretical and practical innovation. Firstly, based on his reflection on stele arts, by absorbing the calligraphic arts from stone tablet inscriptions, He Shaoji delved into the brushwork arts of the Jin and Tang dynasties and integrated the calligraphic arts in stone tablet inscriptions with that of traditional brush calligraphy, with an innovative philosophy of combining different techniques from different calligraphic schools. Secondly, the technique of horizontal and vertical strokes represents a unification between brushwork, structural form, and aesthetics, enclosing such calligraphic and aesthetic elements as the movement of the central axis of the brush, the broad and profound structure, and the transformation of plainness into variability. Thirdly, “deeply study seal script and official script” was the thinking and cognition behind He Shaoji's calligraphy research. In the practice of tablet calligraphy, he advocated the study of selected ancient works, the study of seal script and official script, and the formation of an innovative path of pen integration in practice.

Key Words

He Shaoji, brushwork, aesthetic perspective

Introduction

He Shaoji (1799-1873) was born in Daozhou, Hunan Province (courtesy name Zizhen, art names Dong Zhou Ju Shi (東洲居士), Dong Zhou Shan Ren, and in his later years he adopted the art name Yuansou (猿叟). *Qiu Lin Ba Yu* (《邱林跋語》) said that because of his “hanging arm back to the wrist (懸臂回腕)” writing method, his style takes the meaning of Li Guang ape arm bend bow, as well as Jiu Zi Shan Ren (九子山人) and Si Zhen (耜真). He Shaoji was an active calligrapher in the middle and late Qing Dynasty with high achievements and was an outstanding calligraphy personality. He was one of the four great calligraphers in the Qing Dynasty, alongside

Qian Nanyuan, Liu Shian and Weng Songchan. His educational books covering the Zhou, Qin, and Han ancient seal styles, down to the Six Dynasties north and south tablets, valued the bones but not the posture, self-support, and integration of steles and rubbings, mastering and digesting all those styles. There is “the regular script and running script from the official script differentiation and development; if you want to go deeper, you also need to trace the source of the seal script. (真行原自隸分波, 根巨還求篆籀蝌。)”¹ knowledge, and can draw on the strengths of all schools of thought. His son He Qinghan in the *Xianfu Jun Tomb Table* (《先府君墓表》) concluded that “Calligraphy can be traced back to the seal script and official script, and down to Ouyang Xun

and his son, Yan Zhenqing, Li Yong, Su Dongpo, absorbing and learning various methods to form a unique style of calligraphy art. (書法溯源篆分, 下逮率更父子、魯公、北海、東坡, 神明眾法, 自成一體。)² In the calligraphy fashion of the Qing Dynasty, He Shaoji paid attention to the value of calligraphy, respected Tang calligraphy, and integrated the inscription, which had an enlightening value to the creation of modern Chinese calligraphy.

1. He Shaoji's Innovative Way of Integrating Brushwork

He Shaoji is one of the important representatives of stele calligraphy in the late Qing Dynasty. He reconciled the study of the North stele and the Tang stele and distinguished himself from the “depreciating the Tang style” view represented by Kang Youwei. He could focus on the study of calligraphy, dared to question the theory that calligraphy divides the north and the south in the region, and appreciated the beauty of the stele and rubbing, which was unique among stele calligraphers. He emphasized the individuality and innovation of calligraphy, earnestly analyzed the inscriptions he learned, thought about the artistry of calligraphy based on research and had unique insights about and innovations in penmanship, creation, and writing tools.

The development of his calligraphy art experienced roughly three stages: the enlightenment period (before the age of fifteen), the period of development (sixteen to fifty-six), and the period of maturity (after the age of fifty-six). In the early years, he mainly focused on the Yan style, then studied the calligraphy of the Northern and Southern dynasties extensively in the Middle Ages and made more effort on tablets of the Six Dynasties with strong and robust brushwork. Still, there were few handed down works in this period. In his later years, he devoted himself to seal script, tracing back to the Zhou, Qin, Han, and Wei dynasties, repeatedly studying copying for many years, and copying some works at least a hundred times. He synthesized these influences, incorporating them into his regular script, thereby establishing a unique style. In this mature phase of his artistic journey, He Shaoji's calligraphy became a harmonious blend of accumulated knowledge, extensive learning, and a distinctive personal touch. His approach to small seal script was sporadic, and he valued simplicity over elaboration.

He Shaoji's regular script was based on the Yan style but is rich in connotations. He had worked very hard on *Dao Yin Stele* (《道因碑》), *Zhang He Ru Epitaph* (《張黑女墓誌》), *The Yellow Court Classic* (《黃庭經》), *The*

Buried Cane Epitaph (《瘞鶴銘》), etc. In addition, in the process of deep research on the Tang monument, he found that the seal script could characterize the regular script, and he tried to incorporate the meaning of the seal script into the regular script in his creative practice. However, we can find that although he represents the stele school of calligraphy, he took his method from the Tang Dynasty. In Yan Zhenqing's later years, the meaning of the seal script was obvious, which was a clear change from the typical calligraphy style of the Tang Dynasty and had the characteristics of a simple and grand style. Mi Fu once commented about his *On Seating Arrangement* (《座位帖》) that it contains the flavor and rhythm of both seal script and large seal script (籀), which should be ranked first in Yan Zhenqing's calligraphy works. Its script is mostly used to write plaques and couplets, mainly in the structured Yan style. Ma Zonghuo pointed out in *Sa Yue Lou Essays* (《雲嶽樓筆談》) that He Shaoji's small regular script absorbed the brushwork and aesthetic characteristics of *The Story of Magu's Fairy Altar* (《麻姑仙壇記》), *The Yellow Court Classic* by Wang Xizhi, and *Yueyi Theory* (《樂毅論》), and showed the aesthetic characteristics of harmonious spirit and rich breath. It can be said that after his middle period, his regular script adopted the style of Jin (晉); he saw that Jin was more primitive than Tang, removing the details of Tang's regular technique of dots and twists. This has a great relationship with his *Four Kinds of Ancient Ink in Jin and Tang Dynasties* (《晉唐古墨四種》) in the twenty-third year of Daoguang's reign, among which *The Yellow Court Classic* is a work he particularly appreciated; he once commented: “watching the calligraphy of *The Yellow Court Classic* you can find that the pen starts and stops straight up and down, just like the traces of rain flowing on the wall of a house on a rainy day, it is the ancient ‘roof leak marks’ (屋漏痕) brushwork, the center line, dot the middle of the round. (觀此帖橫直撇捺, 皆首尾直下, 此古屋漏痕法也。)” After that, his small regular script changed. Yang Han said in his small regular script *Huang Ting Nei Jing Yu Jing* (《黃庭內景玉經冊》): “round and vigorous, refined and simple, still inherits the characteristics of Yan Zhenqing and Wang Xizhi's writing style, integrated into his own works, the calligraphy world of hundreds of years of history has been revitalized by this work, such a good small regular script works, is unparalleled in the world. (圓勁精渾, 仍從琅琊上掩山陰, 數百年書法於斯一振, 如此小字, 人間不能有第二本。)”

In his early years, He Shaoji's cursive calligraphy was influenced more by Yan style calligraphy. In his later years, he was influenced by the official script of the

Figure 1. *The Stele of Zhang Qian and He Shaoji Copies the Stele of Zhang Qian* (《何紹基臨張遷碑》).

Han Dynasty. He incorporated the concept of seal script into his cursive script, ultimately developing a unique style. However, it should be noted that his cursive works are rare, and the handed down works are represented by copying Huai Su's calligraphy. Generally speaking, the structure of the cursive script in the mature stage is wide and broad, the transverse potential, the font tends to be square and flat, and the middle palace is dense and uniform; against the trend into the pen, the line wrapped front, the stroke round strength, even flutter processing, with the pen twists and turns; vertical paintings take more arcs, skimming and spreading, like a peng bird about to fly. Regarding the overall characteristics of pen and chapter, the pen needs to enter the paper, keep it, and have astringent meaning, but the whole is smooth, and there is a connection between the words. The structural layout contrast is obvious, and there is stability in the form of risk; twisted, supine opening and closing, oblique and down are all in them, and the novelty of the work is born from this. It is wonderful to hang the wrist and drive the brush with the elbow swing

when writing. Otherwise, it is difficult to grasp the momentum of opening and closing.

He Shaoji's official script matured in his later years (after the age of sixty when he specialized in official script), and he handed down official script mostly during his sixties and seventies. During this period, his imitations can be classified into two types: linxi (faithful copying) and linchuang (creative copying). They often used the meaning of the seal script as the basis for their copying and implemented the concepts of using the middle, horizontal, and vertical strokes. In his approach to linchuang, He Shaoji emphasized incorporating artistic intention. Consequently, many of his representative works were the outcomes of interpreting famous historical inscriptions. His interpretive works often exhibited significant differences from the originals, reflecting his unique calligraphic aesthetic. Notable examples include his interpretations of *The Yellow Court Classic*, *Shi Men Song* (《石門頌》), *The Stele of Zhang Qian* (《張遷碑》) and *The Lushan Temple Stele* (《麓山寺碑》). He saw the seal writing

method from the book of *The Yellow Court Classic*. He thought that Wang Xizhi, Wang Xianzhi and the great calligraphers of the Tang Dynasty all traced their roots to the ancient roof leak marks writing method, while the great calligraphers of the Song Dynasty did not fully abide by this rule. He copied the *Shi Men Song* and *The Stele of Zhang Qian* over a hundred times. He mainly incorporated seal script elements, with horizontal and vertical strokes, using centered tip brushwork that was round and strong. The original tablet on the side is also transformed into the center, and the start and finish of the pen do not pursue the original whole tablet square and seek round strength. In copying the *Shi Men Song*, he first supplemented the original tablet lost by the turning point; second, he brought out the cursive style elements in the official script: "The calligraphy brushwork was unrestrained and ethereal, but was very rigorous. (用筆灑

脫空靈，結構似潦草而實不苟且。)"³ At the age of seventy-one, when he copied *The Heng Fang Tablet* (《衡方碑》), he added vertical momentum to the horizontal style of the official script and incorporated quite a lot of seal meaning. Generally speaking, his interpretive copies often turned the square of the inscription into a circle, pursued the seal meaning, or sought the cursive meaning in the official script and created works based on his understanding of the principles of calligraphic beauty.

Ma Zonghuo spoke highly of his seal script, affirming that he integrated the changing characteristics of large seal script into the seal script so that the characters carved on the ding and yi sacrificial vessels of the Xia, Shang and Zhou dynasties had their creative ideas, and applied the writing method of the ancient ding and yi characters to the writing of small seal script, resulting in

Figure 2. *Shi Men Song* and He Shaoji Copies *Shi Men Song* (《何紹基臨石門頌》).

spiritual exuberation, as if feeling the aesthetic effect of a divine stroke. He learned the seal script and large seal script of the Qin, Han and Six dynasties and focused on absorbing their spiritual rhythms. He often focused on a certain feature of the object, or took the potential, or learned the brush, or learned the structure and distribution of the object—just as when he copied the Han steles—with the focus and method differing during each period while developing and writing different steles.

In general, the basic brushwork and structural laws of He Shaoji's calligraphy are: centered tip brushwork is primary, having horizontal and vertical strokes as the criterion, emphasizing solidity, integrating a variety of calligraphy characteristics, and forming a new calligraphy aesthetic form (such as cursive style elements in the regular and running script); the running elements in seal script become static for moving, moving for quiet, clumsy in strange, there is stability in risk. His creations absorb the characteristics of various masters and open up various styles of writing, especially in his good use of Yanghao (goat hair), seal scripts into cursive scripts, the pursuit of cursive meaning in the official script, the application of herbal writing in the seal script, the tablet in the post, and the risk of nature. His works stood out uniquely in the late Qing Dynasty calligraphy world and still have merit today.

2. Horizontal and Vertical Strokes Change Naturally

From age thirty-two to fifty-seven (1830-1855), He Shaoji mainly drew on the Tang's stele. He deeply understood his father's teachings of horizontal and vertical strokes. Regular script and cursive script benefited from Yan Zhenqing most, and his father and brother were fond of collecting and copying Yan Zhenqing's calligraphy: "Whenever my brothers see Yan Zhenqing's large and small characters works such as *The Story of Magu's Fairy Altar* (《麻姑壇記》), they would collect them. Every time during leisure and quiet moments, we would take out multiple collections to appreciate and evaluate them together. (大小《麻姑壇記》餘弟兄每見即收，每於友於閑靜時，出多本互相評賞。)"⁴ He was diligent in copying Yan's works throughout his life. He never slacked off, and once said: "When I was young, I liked to copy Yan Zhenqing's *On Seating Arrangement*. (少壯時，喜臨《坐位帖》。)"⁵ "I usually use Yan's style to write out all the words of *Zhong Yi Tang* (《忠義堂》), and also collected rubbing works from Song Dynasty: *Ji Bo Wen Gao* (《祭伯文稿》), *Ji Zhi Wen Gao* (《祭侄文稿》), *The Story of Magu's Fairy Altar in Large Character* (《大字麻姑壇記》), *The Monument of Li Xuanjing*. (《李玄靖碑》) (餘平生於顏書手鉤《忠義堂》全部，又收藏宋拓本《祭伯文》《祭

侄文》《大字麻姑壇記》《李元靖碑》。)"⁶ Of course, he also learned from other calligraphers and wrote the regular script around the age of thirty-six (the fourteenth year of Daoguang's reign), and absorbed the lean energy of the Ouyang's style and Zhang Congshen in addition to the Yan style. According to the recollection of his compatriot Lin Changyi, He often taught people to learn calligraphy first from Xu Hao's *Bu Kong He Shang Stele* (《不空和尚碑》) and Ouyang Tong's *Dao Yin Stele*. In his later years, he admired Li Beihai's pursuit of calligraphy in this period. In the winter of the fifteenth year of Daoguang's reign, at the level of imagery, he copied the *Inscription of Shaolin Temple* (《少林寺戒壇銘》) from Li Yong. Around the sixteenth year of Daoguang's reign, he studied Su Shi's calligraphy. In the twenty-third year of Daoguang's reign, he obtained four kinds of ancient calligraphy from the Jin and Tang dynasties, including *The Yellow Court Classic*, Preface to the *Lanting Pavilion* (《定武蘭亭》), *Jade Edition "Thirteen Lines Of Luoshen Fu"* (《玉版十三行》), and *The Story of Magu's Fairy Altar in Small Character* (《小字麻姑壇記》). After that, he became successful in regular script with small characters and was influenced by *The Yellow Court Classic* in its flat and robust form.

Generally speaking, he was greatly influenced by the Tang's stele and styles from Yan and Ouyang throughout his life and was diligent in his studies. During his lifetime, the *Dao Yin Stele* was copied hundreds of times and handed down from generation to generation with seven masterpieces. In addition, he also referred to the calligraphy awareness of the Jin Dynasty. This background in learning about and researching calligraphy allowed him to form a view of horizontal and vertical strokes that integrates structure, brushwork, and aesthetic pursuit.

The phrase "horizontal and vertical strokes" regarding He Shaoji encompasses several dimensions of meaning: centered tip brushwork is primary, maintaining a plain and balanced structure and avoiding excessive tilting. This view of calligraphy is not only about the brushwork but also refers to the conclusion, which reflects the aesthetic pursuit and formal characteristics of the integration of steles and rubbings. This pursuit of calligraphy can be described as the inheritance of calligraphy views from his father and Ruan Yuan, the representative of the stele. He Shaoji once said: "My father, Wen An Gong, has a collection of Song Dynasty rubbings. He copied them for a long time and taught his children 'horizontal and vertical strokes' every time. I widely learned the calligraphy of the Six Dynasties and followed my father's instruction to use 'horizontal and vertical' when learning calligraphy rules. I have held this

opinion about the work of *Zhi Shi Qian Wen* (《智師千文》) for a long time. (先文安公藏宋拓本，臨仿有年，每以“橫平豎直”四字訓兒等。餘肄書汜濫六朝，仰承庭誥，惟以此四字為律令。於《智師千文》持此見久矣。)⁷ In the long-term study of steles and rubbings, his understanding and application of them became more and more free, mainly involving the following aspects.

First, at the core of horizontal and vertical strokes is the centered brushwork. He once talked about seeing Deng Shiru's steles and seal carving with a feeling of empathy, and analyzed Deng Shiru's center stroke and the effect of “quasi-flat and straight (准平繩直).” “Deng's calligraphy has an unprecedented original primitive and elegant beauty. I understand its true meaning. His calligraphy follows the quasi-flat rope straight in the center, and he controls the soft pen with his wonderful wrist strength. The center carries the pen, so the pen does not tilt, but Bao Shichen does not pay attention to the flatness, but uses the flat pen side all over the paper... Mr Deng Shilu also uses a knife to follow the strokes of the center forward, which is similar to his calligraphy strokes. (先生書中古勁橫逸、前無古人之意，則自謂知之最真……先生作書於准平繩直中，自出神力，柔毫勁腕，純用筆心，不使欹斜，備盡轉折，慎翁於平直二字全置不講，扁筆側鋒滿紙俱是……先生作印，使刀如筆，與書律純用筆心者正同。)⁸ It can be seen that the key point of his appreciation of Deng Shiru's calligraphy and seal is his center forward brushwork. Then, he refined the aesthetic characteristics of the center's brushwork, pointing out that this brushwork shows the beauty of breath and roundness. This aesthetic feature is closely related to writing skills and brushwork characteristics; writing only breath through the pen end, light and heavy to follow the heart, “the breath penetrates through it, showing the beauty of harmony, as writing with the center, a stroke in the end and all sides. How can it not be thick, charming, vigorous and far-reaching. (氣貫其中則圓，如寫字用中鋒然，一筆到底四面都有，安得不厚，安得不韻，安得不雄渾，安得不淡遠。)⁹

The second is that horizontal and vertical strokes summarise He Shaoji's stele brushwork. During the rise of tablet science in the Qing Dynasty, an important point of view was that in the long history of stylized development, it had formed a focus on the shortcomings of emphasizing stipple painting at both ends, was weak in the middle sections, low on the left and high on the right fonts and slanting, and tried to strive to correct the shortcomings of the study of steles. He Shaoji emphasized the core beauty of horizontal and vertical strokes and advocated learning from the tablet backbone. He emphasised that the middle part is not empty; it is always solid and thick, full of strength, square shape and

simplicity. In terms of starting and ending the brushwork also appreciated and learned from fighting up and down and straight into and flat out of the North Steles pen, abandoning hiding the head and protecting the tail and other modifying actions, and pursuing the ancient strength and thickness.

Third, the emphasis mentioned above on brushwork finally creates a broad structure, which can be stable in the change and avoids being frivolous. He once said: “Today the world of *The Yellow Court Classic* is from Wu Tongwei imitation model, lost in the repetition of the true meaning of the original, the character is often curved on the left side, extended on the right side, twists and turns to extend the appearance, lost the ancient method, most calligraphers from Yuan and Ming suffered from this shortcomings. (今世《黃庭》皆從吳通微寫本出，又複沿模失真，字勢皆屈左伸右，為斜迤之態，古法遂失，元明書家皆中其弊。)¹⁰ He criticized the attitude of bending the left and stretching the right. He proposed that “Regular script and running script evolved from the division of official script. If you want to go deeper, you need to go back to the source of the seal script. The horizontal and vertical strokes change themselves, and there is no need to skew it to imitate the character ‘Ge’ (戈) written by Yu Shinan to the Emperor Tang Taizong Li Shimin of the Tang. (真行原自隸分波，根巨還求篆籀蝌。豎直橫平生變化，未須欹側效虞戈。)¹¹

In general, He Shaoji's view of horizontal and vertical strokes is manifested in the brushwork of the center forward, where the brushwork is round and the body is wide and broad and produces rich changes in the flat reality. These aesthetics are in harmony with his pursuit of the unity of personality and calligraphy, the gentleness of the air, and the innovation of separating seal characters into practice. Pan Tianshou once said, “‘To the largest, to the just, to the middle, to the right’ is stored in the ‘mind’, and ‘art’, you can reach the ‘peak’.” (至大、至剛、至中、至正) 蘊蓄於胸中，“旁及藝事”，就能達到“登峰造極”的地步。¹² His view of art also proves from one side that He Shaoji's view of brushwork and artistic achievements are closely linked with a subjective outlook on life and that the outlook on life makes the view of art.

3. To Deepen the Ancient Methods of Seal Script and Official Script to Achieve the Beauty of Strong Character

He Shaoji's study books always followed the principle of fine ancient. The meaning of fine ancient has two aspects: first, in terms of the copy and study of the rubbing from the inscription, it is necessary to select the

inscription carefully and not overdo it, choosing the ancient clumsy ones instead of the stylized and kitschy ones; and second, in terms of calligraphy modeling and artistic conception, it is also necessary to refine the ancient, learn the essence of the charm, and not stop at the appearance. His life, carefully studied, is its very representative seal script method inscription. He once said, “I like the North Steles, so I imitate more... However, in terms of the simple and unsophisticated aesthetic feeling, no epitaph can be as famous as the epitaph of *Zhang Hei Ru Epitaph* (《張黑女》墓誌). I have bought and collected more such inscriptions, which are very exquisite because they combine the brushwork of seal script and official script into the regular script. (餘既性嗜北碑, 故摹仿甚勤, ……然適厚精古, 未有可比肩《黑女》者, 而購藏亦富, 化篆分入楷, 遂爾無種不妙, 無妙不臻。)”¹³

Thus, it can be seen that what he is pursuing is the ancient classic and that he chose the North Steles. From the point of view of the Tang Dynasty, he pointed out that regular script was learned first to deeply appreciate the “calligrapher proficient in seal” method, then running script or cursive script. “There were many calligraphers in the Tang Dynasty, but those who understood seal script and official script in writing were only Ouyang Xun first, and then Yan Zhenqing, Yu Shinan, Chu Suiliang, and others can not be compared with them. Anyone not intimately acquainted with the origins of seal script, official script, regular script and cursive script would not believe this view... When I first started to learn calligraphy, I imitated *Huadu Temple Stele* (《化度寺碑》) and *Jiu Cheng Gong Li Quan Ming* (《九成宮醴泉銘》), just like crossing the sea without a sail. (有唐一代, 書家林立, 然意兼篆分, 涵包萬有, 則前惟渤海, 後惟魯國, 非虞、褚諸公所並能頡頏也。此論非深於篆分真草源流本末者, 固不能信。……若初學執筆, 便模仿《化度》《醴泉》, 譬之不掛帆而涉海耳。)”¹⁴ He Shaoji spent half his life working on *The Story of Magu’s Fairy Altar*, *On Seating Arrangement* (《爭坐位帖》), *Dao Yin Stele*, *The Lushan Temple Stele* (《麓山寺碑》) and other Tang steles, from which he discovered and excavated the seal characters. Although he also wrote seal characters and official script during this period, his early achievements still benefited from Tang steles. In his later years, he learned from Tang steles and combined them with tablet science. It was fused into his unique aesthetic pursuit of calligraphy and, unified with his self-created writing method in his later years and combined with the creation of running and cursive script, formed a mature calligraphy style with unique characteristics.

He Shaoji immersed himself in the study of the seal method and formed a unique way of writing force: the

(1854), he wrote a poem *Yuan Bi Weng* (《猿臂翁》) during his academic administration in Sichuan, which gave a clear explanation of this principle of the method: “the law of calligraphy writing is similar to the principle of archery, and the valuable thing is that the arms are suspended in the air and kept in a round and empty state. With a simple method to deal with complex situations, constant changes, and a simple body and mind to control a variety of pen movements, one can live in the reality of the pen between nothingness. Li was gifted at shooting, and his long, ape-like arms were more than just two arms. Qi from the sole of the feet until the fingers, this is the overall embodiment of luck force; the first overall side has the details of the ‘exquisite’ ingenious, bending straight, advancing and retreating freely. (書律本與射理同, 貴在懸臂能圓空。以簡禦煩靜制動, 四面滿足吾居中。李將軍射本天授, 猿臂豈止兩臂通。氣自踵息極指項, 屈伸進退皆玲瓏。)” This method of writing had been proposed before, although it is not completely consistent with He Shaoji’s perspective. However, there are similarities in the principles of writing. For example, Dong Qichang believes that the Tang people used the wrist method to create calligraphy. The pen can be reserved, and the pen is not straightforward and smooth. That is, the suspender center, the line is calm and powerful. Huang Tingjian believes that “the method of using the pen is to hook the pen tube with the index finger and middle finger, hold the finger firmly when writing, and the outer four fingers should be close to each other, dense and not loose. Palm to the void, ring finger and little finger do not stick to the palm, with the ring finger against the pen, writing will have strength, convenient, flexible force. (用筆之法, 欲雙鉤回腕, 掌虛指實, 以無名指倚筆, 則有力。)” He also said: “When learning to write, first use the index finger and middle finger hook the pen, gather the pen pressure on the ring finger, the higher position to hold the pen, so that the wrist can move around freely according to the will. (凡學字時, 先當雙鉤, 用兩指相疊, 蹙筆壓無名指, 高提筆, 令腕隨己意左右。)”¹⁵ The key point of the ancient people’s wrist is to stay, use the ring finger to force, increase the friction between the pen and paper, and increase the astringent feeling. This is similar to the technical effect pursued by He Shaoji’s brushwork; the difference is that He Shaoji worked with the elbow rather than the wrist. In general, this contrarian writing method is unified with the simplicity, thickness and change of seal script, forming the contrarian beauty of its brushwork. “As far as its writing is concerned, the cantilever wrist must condense the pen end with the force of the whole body, which is against the physiological characteristics of the writing method often let him return to the wrist high, the strength

wrist method. In the fourth year of Xianfeng's reign of the whole body to the pen end to write, each time the writing is less than half, the sweat wet the clothes, (from *Zhang He Ru Epitaph*, 每一臨寫, 必回腕高懸, 通身力到, 方能成字, 約不及半, 汗浹衣襦矣。)" but after long-term training has produced a strange writing effect, there are changes in dignity. He Shaoji's calligraphy starts with the reverse, where the first stroke of each word is the reverse, round and firm. His brushwork can be said to be exaggerated to reflect the ups and downs in Zhang Huaiguan's *Ten Methods on Using the Pen* (《論用筆十法》): "The brushwork quickly reverses and adjusts the brushwork, and the pen naturally fricts on the paper to form the shape of peaks and mountains. At the end of the pen, it is like a sudden brake, which cannot end suddenly but must have a certain stop. (起筆蹙衄, 如峰巒之狀, 殺筆亦須存結。)"¹⁶

He Shaoji obtained the essence of the Yan style in his early years of learning Tang stele and formed the style of Yan style. His regular script skill was his deepest, and he was successful by the age of forty. The style and brushwork of Yan style characters determine its basic style. In his later years, the combination of the writhing method and the seal script method greatly changed the form and structure of calligraphy, forming a unique personal style.

He strengthened brushwork in the official script, where the horizontal character was especially strengthened starting from the lower left. As far as the operation of long lines is concerned, the natural stop and swing increase the astringency and vibration of the lines, and there is a beauty of change. The contrast of stippling is also more obvious, such as boulders falling to the peak or orchid leaves gently blowing. The application of raw rice paper and the edge of the sheep hair forms a strange effect. The structure seeks stability while being strange, and leaving blank space means it can be sparse and airtight; pay great attention to the contrast and collocation of ink color, font size, late astringent fluency, etc., seek harmony in the change, and seek stability in the strange. From his cursive writing, we can see the seal meaning brought by his brushwork. He often draws the beauty of straightness from *Dao Yin Stele* and has a steep and steep air in his cursive script. Its "back wrist high hanging" way of writing, out of the front can also be generalized to the left and right stretch, the pursuit of "clumsy late" beauty, to avoid the rash and slippery problems that appear easily in the study of the post. As far as the knot is concerned, it is naturally relaxed, there is a strong contrast in size, and the ink color is naturally thick and dry. Generally speaking, his calligraphy pays special attention to the importance of the brush, is good

at working on the dry and wet color of the ink, and the dense opening and closing of the composition so the works appear rich in change, have a sense of rhythm, and have a strong visual impact. Its condensed lines have a strong sense of strength but appear soothing and full of internal force. He is seeking new, and seeking risk is not abandoning the tradition; on the contrary, it goes back to the Zhou, Qin and Han dynasties' seal division, so that its running, cursive, and regular scripts have seal division, thus becoming a brand of his own. "To restore the ancient meaning of calligraphy, cleanse and clean up the vulgarity of calligraphy. (古意挽可回, 俗書期一蕩。)"¹⁷ "To create the situation of seal script and official script between writing, and to sweep away the style of calligraphy. (腕間創出篆分勢, 掃盡古來姿媚格。)"¹⁸ He believes that Yan's work wins with simplicity, which is the extreme of the beauty of change, or it can be said that the beauty of change lies in simplicity. "The image of each stele of Yan's style is different, and its simplicity is unique, which is the source of change. (顏書各碑, 意象種種不同, 此碑獨以樸勝, 正是變化狡獪之極耳。)"¹⁹ The mellow and primitive nature of the book can not be done deliberately; otherwise, it will lose its natural beauty. "The artistic beauty of calligraphy, as described by the bent hairpin and the leaking rain on the house traces, should be natural... But if it is deliberately artificial, it will certainly not be smooth. (折釵股, 屋漏痕, 特形容之辭, 機到神來...有意為之, 必成頓滯。)"²⁰ Finally, the in-depth study of the seal and official script achieved the aesthetic characteristics of natural changes in ancient calligraphy.

4. Conclusion

He Shaoji held an important position in the literary circle of the Qing Dynasty. Thanks to his dialectical vision in theoretical cognition, he did not unthinkingly follow the theoretical trend of stele worship and scribing but firmly based his position on practical investigation. He emphasized the principle of separating characters in the writings of the Jin and Tang dynasties. He realized the importance of the complementarity of tablets and scribing to the innovation of calligraphy. He also realistically summarized their possible and integrable paths, forming the brushwork concepts of horizontal and vertical strokes and deeply studying seal script and official script, which laid the foundation for the aesthetic pursuit of natural changes and strong bones. What is commendable is that he implemented theoretical cognition into the creation practice and was the one who could confirm the theory with practice in the trend of epigraphy in the Qing Dynasty. He brought rich artistic

achievements for the practice of epigraphy, and the strong unity of academic theory and talent promoted the development of epigraphy in the Qing Dynasty. He also had great enlightenment value for the innovation of con-

temporary calligraphy.

*Arctic Research Center on School of Foreign Languages,
Liaocheng University*

Project Source: National Social Science Fund Education Project, Construction and Implementation Research on the New Era Calligraphy Aesthetic Education System. (Project Approval Number: BLA220238)

HAO CHUNYAN (1977-), Ph.D., professor and master supervisor at the School of Foreign Languages, Liaocheng University. Postdoctoral fellow of Capital Normal University, visiting scholar at Beijing Normal University. Research focuses on art theory, art aesthetics and art education.

Editor: Yao Xiao

ENDNOTES

1. He Shaoji, "A Summary of the Stele of Wu Temple Hall in Guanzhongcheng," in *Selected Notes on He Shaoji's Writings*, ed. He Shuzhi (Hunan: Hunan Fine Arts Publishing House, 1988), 68.
2. He Qinghan, "Tomb Table of Xianfujun," in *95th Series of Modern Chinese Historical Materials* (Taiwan: Wenhai Publishing House, 1966), 12.
3. Hai Dictionaries Publishing House, ed., *He Shaoji's Ode to Shimen* (Shanghai: Shanghai Dictionaries Publishing House, 2009), 1.
4. He Shaoji, "The Old Rubbage of Magu Mountain Xiantan," in *He Shaoji's Poetry Collection II* (Hunan: Yuelu Publishing House, 2008), 812.
5. He Shaoji, "After the Old Linsat Post," in *He Shaoji's Book Commentary* (Hunan: Hunan Fine Arts Publishing House, 1988), 147.
6. He Shaoji, "Reengraving Li Beihai's Stele of Fahua Temple," in *He Shaoji's Poetry Collection II* (Hunan: Yuelu Publishing House, 2008), 809.
7. He Shaoji, "Qian Zhi Shi," in *He Shaoji's Poetry Collection I* (Hunan: Yuelu Publishing House, 2008), 402.
8. He Shaoji, "Deng Wanbai's Book After Printing," in *He Shaoji's Book Commentary* (Hunan: Hunan Fine Arts Publishing House, 1988), 31.
9. He Shaoji, "Nineteen Rules of Poetry with Wang Jushi," in *He Shaoji's Poetry Collection II* (Hunan: Yuelu Publishing House, 2008), 733.
10. He Shaoji, "The Yellow Court Classic," in *He Shaoji's Poetry Collection II* (Hunan: Yuelu Publishing House, 2008), 795.
11. He Shaoji, "Zhou Yunchen (Wen Yu) Temple Stele of Guan Zhong Cheng Wu II," in *He Shaoji's Poetry Collection I* (Hunan: Yuelu Publishing House, 2008), 373.
12. Hao Wenjie, "Pan Tianshou's Theory on the Creation of Truth in Painting and its Educational Value," *Art Magazine* 2 (2023): 50.
13. He Shaoji, "Rubbing of Zhang He Ru Epitaph," in *He Shaoji's Poetry Collection II* (Hunan: Yuelu Publishing House, 2008), 798.
14. He Shaoji, *He Shaoji's Poetry Collected II*, ed. Long Zhenqiu and He Shuzhi (Hunan: Yuelu Publishing House, 2008) 802-803.
15. East China Normal University, *Selected Essays on Calligraphy in the Past Dynasties* (Shanghai: Shanghai Calligraphy and Painting Publishing House, 1979), 355-356.
16. *Ibid.*, 216.
17. He Shaoji, "Li Zhongheng Wang Qiu Cha has Hui poetry push Xu Zhuo books are written in cheng rhyme this explanation [李仲衡王秋垞先後惠詩推許拙書皆用中丞韻賦此荅之]," ed. He Shuzhi *Selected Notes on He Shaoji's Books* (Hunan: Hunan Fine Arts Publishing House, 1988), 144.
18. He Shaoji, "Shi Jiao Tu Poem, Written by Deng Shouzhi," in *He Shaoji's Poetry Collection II* (Hunan: Yuelu Publishing House, 2008), 584.
19. He Shaoji, *He Shaoji's Poetry Collection*, ed. Long Zhenqiu and He Shuzhi (Hunan: Yuelu Publishing House, 2008), 810.
20. *Ibid.*, 813.

何紹基筆法特徵及審美取向研究

郝春燕

摘要: 何紹基是清代書法藝術成就的重要代表,在碑學“卑唐”的時風中他能敏銳地關注到帖學筆法與碑學互補的重要價值,在融合對話的創新路上形成“橫平豎直”和“精古篆分”的筆法觀,從而也形成了其書法圓渾質樸、骨力雄健、變化自然的書法審美特徵。筆法在何紹基書法藝術思想中有重要地位,是其理論和實踐創新的重要切入點:一、何紹基主要通過碑學反思,深入唐晉筆法發現篆分筆意,最終在碑帖意臨和以臨入創中探索了多不同書體之間筆法互融的創新之路;二、“橫平豎直”是筆法、結體和審美統一的筆法觀,包孕了中鋒運筆,結體寬博,平實生變化等書寫和審美特徵;三、“精古篆分”是何紹基筆法研究的思路和認知,在碑帖臨習中他提倡學習精選古作,研習“篆分之法”,並在實踐中形成筆法融匯的創新路徑。

關鍵詞: 何紹基; 筆法; 審美觀